

Gearing Roles Project Handbook

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Information in this report that may influence other GEARING ROLES tasks

Linked Task	Points of Relevance
T.2.1	Project Oversight and Management
T.2.2.	Organization of project meetings
T.8.1	Development of a Dissemination Plan

GEARING ROLES project

GEARING-Roles is a four-year (January 2019 – December 2022) Coordination and Support Action project that will bring together a pan-European group of academics and industry professionals to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned on designing, implementing, and evaluating 6 Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The project therefore has a firm objective of challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers and working towards real institutional change. This multidisciplinary, multinational, and multi-sectorial collaboration will be supported by training in this space, mentoring activities, awareness raising campaigns as well as bi-annual videos and podcasts and annual networking events.

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List of Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
E-UC	End-User Community
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisations
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
WP	Work Package
UDEUSTO	Universidad de Deusto
IGOT-UL	Instituto Du Geografía y Ordenamento, Universidade de Lisboa
UL	University of Ljubljana
SU	Sabancı University
OBU	Oxford Brookes University
ETAg	Estonian Research Council
YW	Yellow Window
FEYCIT	Fundación Española de Ciencia Y Tecnología (Coordinadores Euraxess España)
TRI	Trilateral Research
RAD	Radboud University
GEP:	Gender Equality Plan
GMO	Gearing Roles Management Office
GSC	GEARING-Roles Steering Committee
GSI	GEARING-Roles Supporting Institutions
PSO	Project Scientific Coordinator
PCO	Project Coordinator
FO	Financial Officer

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Executive Summary

This document serves as the Project Handbook of the GEARING Roles project (Grant Agreement Nr.: 824536) to be used as a guide throughout the whole implementation period. It describes the administrative rules and processes discussed and laid down during the proposal writing period and the Kick-off Meeting, in the Consortium Agreement and in the Quality and Monitoring Plan of the project. This handbook has been prepared to ensure the smooth execution of the project.

1. Project Organisational Structure

Project Work Plan Structure

GEARING-Roles adopts the **5 steps methodology for implementing GEPs outlined by the GEAR tool and follows the gender mainstreaming circle**. The project is structured around a transnational community so that: “together, the professional researcher and the stakeholders define the problems to be examined, cogenerate relevant knowledge about them, learn and execute social research techniques, take actions, and interpret the results of actions based on what they have learned” (Greenwood and Levin 2007, p. 3).

GEARING-Roles is thus based on organised participation of researchers and practitioners and on “learning by doing” (Wenger and Snyder 2000). It builds up capacities of GEP implementing beneficiaries throughout the accession process, resulting in progressive, positive developments in the participating institutions. Institutional pairing aims to share good practices developed within participating institutions and other organisations akin at the European level, and to foster long-term relationships between partners and other EU key actors. Project partners are institutions with sufficient staff and absorption capacity to work with other partner institution having a similar structure and mandate. GEARING-Roles partners mobilise their staff, demonstrate enduring commitment and ownership and take on board changes and best practices in a sustainable way. Hence, pairing system is not a one-way technical assistance instrument but a shared commitment. GEP implementing institutions have expressly addressed their commitment at the top level, which is considered as a success factor (EIGE 2016: 31). By developing peer-to-peer learning processes GEP implementing institutions will address both the opportunities and limitations of real-life implementation and foster the debate and exchange of experience between organisations’ representatives, independent experts and other relevant stakeholders

Step 1: Understand the context. This includes an analysis of the participating institutions’ unique situations to inform the design and implementation of the GEPs and ensure their relevance and impact. GEARING-Roles will help understand how environment and cultural contexts determine the value of different degrees and professional settings through a sound analysis of the socio-political and normative contexts at the regional and national levels under WP3 (Cultural and Environmental Assessment. This contextual analysis should also include efforts to seek support and alliances from both within and beyond the institutions.

Fig. 1 Project workplan structure.

Step 2: Evaluate the state-of-play in the institution. This second step involves an in-depth diagnosis of the current state of women and men in their institutions by defining as many quantitative and qualitative indicators as possible, collecting relevant data pertaining to them, and opening up spaces for participation. This assessment will help partners evaluate how gender roles and identities are performed in each GEP implementing institutions in terms of disaggregated data of staff, degrees and professional ranks. WP3 will also conduct an appraisal of the differences and similarities between different types of

research organisations and disciplines and outline guidelines on factors and indicators in STEM and SSH taking intersectionality into account.

Step 3. Plan and set up a GEP. For GEPs to be integrated and holistic its conceptual and design coherence should be ensured. GEARING-Roles aims at designing GEPs that involve a deeper and strategic understanding of the sociology and psychology of gender roles.

Step 4. Act and implement the GEPs. The implementation of GEPs will follow an agreed timeline. It will be accompanied by periodic meetings of joint committees on equality (GEPI). This committee will be attended by people in charge of the GEP implementation at each institution and might also engage university rectors, directors, head of departments, and union delegates when necessary. These meetings aim to facilitate a participatory approach that in turn enhances the ownership of the GEPs and deepens the adopted measures' impact. A first joint session will be arranged to foster camaraderie as well as discuss and establish the context and the timeline of GEPs' implementation. Furthermore, follow-up meetings, monitoring sessions, and a dedicated WP (WP7 for Capacity Building) will be established to resolve issues, answer questions and provide support. WPs 4 to 6 will work on different issues (career development, leadership and research) to support the implementation of the GEPs

Step 5. Monitor progress and evaluate the effectiveness of GEPs. We will establish indicators of progress and real impact. WP9 will coordinate and supervise the process, coherence, and results through ex-ante, mid-term, and ex-post evaluations. WP9 will closely collaborate with the designated structure in each institution that implements the GEPs in designing and identifying the indicators for evaluation. These will be aligned with GEP Implementing Institutions own objectives, potential, and limitations.

GEARING-Roles approach is a combination of integration and decentralisation strategies. Integration through the composition of a consortium with complementary skills and knowledge, the development of a joint framework of common guidelines, broad network of supporting institutions and project events and conferences. The resources of all partners will be mobilised by decentralisation of responsibilities through the assignment of leadership of WPs and the implementation of the GEPs; a clear task-sharing that leads to efficient decision-making mechanisms and a sound financial management safeguarding the achievement of the project's objectives.

A concise implementation plan with a clear set of control points throughout the project's lifespan. GEARING-Roles has paid special attention to balance the staff dedication in the central Work Packages

(2-8) allowing a well-adjusted tasks distribution and necessary workload to achieve project objectives. WP 2-8 are all provided with 50PM, distributed among project partners according to their roles and responsibilities in each WP. WP leadership has been assigned with similar PM account considering partners' profiles and experience

Project Management Structure

GEARING-Roles' organisation and management structure will ensure a comprehensive and coherent support across the Consortium for the implementation of the project. It will provide a quality-assurance system, not only enhancing the quality of the actions carried out but also promoting transparent, accountable procedures throughout the project's lifetime.

A Consortium Agreement (CA) has been signed at the outset detailing the procedures and to guarantee and efficient management. The CA covers, among other aspects, the governance structure and decision-making processes, the allocation of financial resources to the beneficiaries and the rules for exploitation and dissemination of results. The CA sets up mechanisms for conflict resolution, including a mediation procedure, to settle any dispute that may arise within the network.

Figure 1: Gearing Roles Management Structure

Fig. 2 Gearing Roles Management Structure

2. Project Timescale

Fig. 3. Gearing Roles Timeline

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3. Project Roles and Responsibilities

Project Coordinator

GEARING-Roles is coordinated by UDEUSTO and led by Deusto Gender Interdisciplinary Research Platform. UDEUSTO will be the primary contact point with the EC and the primary responsible for resource control and procedures applied to ensure efficient progress from a technical, administrative and financial point of view, including the timely achievement of the milestones and delivery of project results. The coordination of the project is shared by Professor María Silvestre Cabrera (PSO), as scientific coordinator and María López Belloso (PhD) as project coordinator(PC).

GEARING-Roles Management Office

UDEUSTO as coordinator will centralise the day-to-day management comprising a Project Scientific Coordinator (PSO), Project Coordinator (PC), and a Financial Officer (FO), and will be in charge of the technical and financial management of the project. The GMO will also ensure that internal communications across the consortium, and with associate partners and stakeholders, are regular and fluid, either through face-to-face meetings or electronic means. The PM Team will be supported by other units at UDEUSTO such as the International Research Projects Office, the HR Department, Legal and Financial Offices, etc., all of them with wide experience in European project implementation. UDEUSTO was a pioneering university in European project coordination and management in Spain; it currently participates in the smooth running of more than 20 EU-funded projects per year. Each beneficiary will identify the unit in charge of the management (including administrative, legal and financial processes) at each organisation, and ongoing communication between those and the PM Team to monitor the implementation of the project according to the Grant Agreement and EC rules and to provide necessary inputs for reporting.

The GMO will be responsible for the administrative management and provide assistance towards all partners concerning: Rules and contracts of the project; outline of the Consortium Agreement; distribution of European funding according to the Consortium Agreement; project planning and individual partner planning; personal advice; practical organisation of the Steering Committee meetings; follow up of the on-time scientific reporting with the GEPI Committee and preparation of on-time scientific reporting to the Commission; periodic monitoring and reporting of the expenses and allocation of the budget in coordination with GEPI and work package leaders.

GEARING-Roles Steering Committee

GEARING-Roles Steering Committee (GSC) will take operational decisions necessary for the smooth execution of the project. It will consist of a representative of every member meeting, chaired by the PC. It is the decision-making body and will mainly deal with issues concerning the relationship between the members and major strategic issues in the project, taking operational decisions necessary for the smooth execution of the project. The GSC will meet once a year and coinciding with Annual Conferences (M12, M24, M36, M46) to save time and resources. GSC will entail not only the formal meetings for strategic decision making and project monitoring, but also informal meetings and activities that will help to strengthen the links between GEARING-Roles members and to engage new partnerships. Besides, much of the activity of the project will be carried out through the e-community, as a means to collaborate and foster exchanges on issues and topics related to structural change. It will allow representatives of the beneficiaries, supporting institutions and stakeholders to discuss technical matters, describe needs and constraints and defining common strategies and challenges.

In addition, GSC will hold e-meetings every three months for a proper follow up and monitoring of project activities and to enable a smooth functioning. Decision making, voting and conflict resolution processes, which are explained in more detail in the signed Consortium Agreement (CA). Such processes are well thought to match the complexity and scale of the project, in particular having in mind that GEARING-Roles project is composed of 10 partners of different profiles, characteristics and countries. As is also stipulated in the CA, the GSC shall not deliberate and decide validly unless two-thirds (2/3) of its Members are present or represented (quorum). Each Member shall have one vote. The GSC will work on consensual decisions as much as possible and resort to voting only if unavoidable. Voting decisions shall be taken by a majority of two-thirds (2/3) of votes. The Parties agree to abide by all decisions of the GSC This does not prevent Parties from submitting a dispute for resolution

GEPI Implementing Institutions Committee (GEPI)

The GEP Implementing Institutions Committee (GEPI) will gather a representative of each of the GEP implementing institutions to deal with the task and activities related to their implementation. In line with the responsible control of resources, this committee will meet in parallel with the pairing visits described above (M6, M11, M18, M23, M30, M35), and with the three annual conferences or online. This organ will deal with the task related to the implementation of the plans and foster the knowledge exchange between the GEPI members and will also establish a continuous online communication among its members every 3 months. Yellow Window, WP7 leader and responsible of the capacity building and provision of support for the GEP implementation will chair this committee.

Work package leaders

The work package leaders coordinate their respective work packages and monitor the tasks to be performed by participating consortium members to ensure realization of the proposed time line (see Gantt Chart in the work plan).

Table 1. WP Leaders

WP1	University of Deusto
WP2	University of Deusto
WP3	University of Ljubljana
WP4	FEYCIT
WP5	University of Deusto
WP6	Oxford Brookes University
WP7	Yellow Window
WP8	Trilateral
WP9	Radboud University

The coordination entails all aspects of including the planning of tasks, specification of the contribution of each partner, resource planning and the timely achievement of milestones and deliverables. Every work package leader will be supported by staff members from their own institutes and, if necessary, by the GSC, ensuring close collaboration within the work packages.

GEARING-Roles Supporting Institutions

The involvement of stakeholders and networks and the dissemination of results are crucial to the project success. We aim to organise the input from the GSIs from the beginning of the project. We mean to organise the SIs from several network groups and have yearly meetings during the GSM Meetings. The SIs will be structured according to the type of SIs (Public bodies and policy makers; European and International Networks and projects; Companies (private sector); and agencies).

Table 2. List of Supporting Institutions

Institution name	Organisation type	Location
Leadership Foundation	Private company	UK
AESIS	Research Association	The Netherlands
GARAGE ERASMUS	Research Association	Italy
AERNOVA	Private company	Spain
IFEES	Research Association	USA
GEDC	Research Association	USA
CIG	Policy Maker	Portugal
VITA ACTIVA	Gender Equality Association	Slovenia
EDIW	International Association	Italy
EMAKUNDE	Policy Making	Spain
UNIBASQ	Research Funding Organization	Spain
ESTONIAN MINISTRY EDUCATION AND RESEARCH	Policy Maker	Estonia
VELATIA	Private company	Spain
Mujeres por Africa	International Organisation	Spain
Dutch Network of Women Professors (LNVH)	Research Association	The Netherlands
Unidad de mujer y Ciencia	Policy Maker	Spain
UNICA	Research Association	Belgium
SCIENCE BUSINESS	Research Association	Belgium
SANTANDER	Private company (BANK)	Spain
GEDII	Previous EU Funded project	
GENERA	Previous EU Funded project	

SAGE	Previous project	EU	Funded	
PLOTINA	Previous project	EU	Funded	

GEARING-Roles External Advisory Board of external experts

It will meet three times in the course of the project and will also be invited to the Final event in Brussels. It will provide intellectual guidance and feedback on the scientific aspects of the project. Proposed members of the Scientific Advisory Board are **Marloes Van Engen, Annabel Martin, Octavio Salazar and Gary Barker**. This Advisory board will be chaired by Marloes Van Engen, who is Gender Policy Advisor for Tilburg University and assistant professor at the Department of Human Resource Studies. Annabel Martin, former Director of the Gender Research Institute at Dartmouth (GRID), which is flagship organization for interdisciplinary gender-based research, will bring her expertise on US Gender system. Octavio Salazar is a Spanish jurist, expert in Constitutional Law and specially in equality and new masculinities. He is member of the Feminist Network of Constitutional Law and the Men for Equality network. He has published numerous books and articles on hegemonic masculinity and the use of stereotypes and has been awarded with the 2017 Progressive Man Award for his teaching and research work on gender equality, new masculinities, cultural diversity and LGBTI rights. Gary Barker is International Director and founder of Promundo, an international NGO and co-chair and co-founder of Men Engage, a global alliance of more than 400 NGOs and UN agencies working to engage men and boys in gender equality, and a member of the UN Secretary General's Men's Leaders Network to end violence against women. Therefore, this gender balanced Advisory board, relying on the experience of its external experts will contrast the progresses and the work developed by the community with key experts that could feed back and contribute both from other gender equality experiences.

4. Project Communication

During the implementation of the Gearing Roles Project, a dedicated WP (WP8 for Dissemination and Outreach) will also ensure that communication flows smoothly within and between participating institutions. This is a fundamental task that goes along with the development of the Institutional Pairing (WP7) for internal communication and Communication and Engagement Strategy for external correspondences and networking.

a) Internal communication

In coordination with WP2, WP7 will develop a Knowledge Sharing Strategy with two main goals:

1. to promote the active participation and engagement among all the consortium partners. This involves setting up an Intranet system with forum and discussion features for sharing progress and reflections. A summary of learnings, challenges, and effective strategies in engaging with a wider community will be shared with all GEARING-Roles partners and key institutional players in the form of Knowledge Sharing Progress Reports released bi-annually.
2. to define the strategy to share information using the main channels, both online and institutional to maximize the diffusion of the knowledge

b) Communication and Engagement Strategy for external correspondences and networking

It will specify the plan and the avenues for engagement using inclusive language and non-stereotypical images as recommended by the GEAR Tool. In the elaboration and implementation of such strategy, the consortium partners will take on a decisive and engaged role. The Communication strategy will involve both physical and online engagement. Brochures, posters, and screens will be utilised during face-to-face and on-campus events. Meanwhile, communication platforms will be created for greater visibility, putting special focus on social media strategies via Facebook and Twitter to extend our reach and impact. For this purpose, WP7 will identify target audiences and main accounts in different social networks to help the dissemination and impact of project outcomes. Strong emphasis will be given to the visibility of GEPs not only within each consortium members, but also at external and dissemination events. At the same time, special care will be taken in the presentation and informational content regarding the progress of all partners in their GEPs, ensuring that they are timely and aligned with the objectives set out during the planning phase. Progress will be disseminated within the participating institution, and with the wider community, exhausting all possible means of offline and online communication. Each partner will commit to contributing in raising awareness on the issue of gender inequality and increasing the visibility of the project by sharing posts and updates on their corporate accounts using high-engagement hashtags as it will help to create ownership and strengthen the potential of the implemented actions.

Mailing lists

Email is the main tool in GEARING Roles for internal communication. There are 6 mailing lists that were created:

- 1.-GR-ALL
- 2.-Project coordination & Management
- 3.-Project Financial Office
- 4.-Stakeholders Community
- 5.-Advisory Board
- 6.-GEP Implementing Institutions Committee"

All mailing lists are managed by DEUSTO. Any request to add or remove a member from any of the project mailing lists should be sent directly to DEUSTO.

In addition, WP Leaders may create mailing lists to address the participants contributing to each WP in particular. Such mailing lists will be managed by the corresponding WP leader. Therefore, any request to add or remove a member from a WP mailing list should be sent directly to the corresponding WP Leader.

An automatic identifier [GEARING ROLES] appears in the Subject of the email when using one of the mailing lists. It is necessary to indicate a description of the content of the email in the subject to facilitate the processing by the different partners.

Videoconferences

Conference calls are arranged as often as needed. An agenda needs to be sent in advance to the participants, and short conference call minutes are produced after the call and shared with the participants, with actions and assigned tasks included in the document.

Skype and Blackboard Collaborate are used by the Project Coordinator. Partners are free to use a different system depending on the internal facilities of each partner.

Knowledge transfer Platform

UDEUSTO will develop a knowledge sharing platform. Main features of the platform are

- Self-hosted solution (so the data are stored in our servers), flexible (powered by third party tools) and open source, to improve the source code if it is necessary.
- Social communication oriented. It is mandatory to engage the user to use this tool, so it should be very user-friendly and oriented to make the communication between members easy.
- Creation of different spaces, both public and private. To use it as document management tool, to share documents, media files and discuss about it, and as social network of the GEARING ROLES project. Should be easy to find spaces, users and groups in the platform.
- Creation of rich profiles, create your portfolio, connect with other people, find the right person with special skills, inform your followers with updates on your own wall and so on.
- Mobile ready, to be used in modern devices like smartphones and tablets.

First version of the Platform will be available by the end of M2

Consortium Meetings

A number of face-to-face meetings are going to be organised throughout the project to promote interactions and exchanges among the partners. These meetings will be held in parallel with ACs and Pairing visits and the estimated length is 1 and half day.

Participants to the meeting need to be warned in advance to be able to make the necessary travel arrangements. Likewise, the agenda of the meeting shall be sent at least 3 weeks in advance (or only 10 days in the case of an extraordinary meeting). Minutes of the meeting will be drafted and circulated among the partners for comments no later than 10 days after the meeting takes place

The following face-to-face meetings have been organized so far:

Kick-off meeting (Bilbao, 17-18 January 2019) – already celebrated.

First Meeting. Lisbon (27/28 Nov 2019)

Second Meeting. Istanbul (Around 20th Nov 2020)

Third Meeting. Tartu. (Around 25 Nov 2021)

Fourth Meeting: Brussels October 2022

5. Data and Deliverables

This section outlines the methodology for the creation and, if necessary, approval of documents. Quality assurance (QA) measures are only applied to paper documents produced within the project. The aim of QA measures is to guarantee the quality of the project results. Each WP leader is responsible for the quality of results generated within his/her WP, especially of the deliverables that, as described below, will be subject to a peer review.

- **Paper documents** (management reports, project deliverables, etc.) must go through at least two QA iterations:
 - To achieve status “draft” (starting with version v01) it should be internally reviewed by the author(s) of the document;
 - To achieve status “draft n^o” it needs to be reviewed and approved from project members other than the main author(s) of the document. Two independent reviewers, each one from one GEARING Roles partners, shall identify if something is missing, if there is an inconsistency between sentences, if something is superfluous (not useful or not appropriate in the deliverable) or any other issue. A quality review form will be included at the end of each deliverable (see Annex III - Deliverable review form for deliverable quality assessment);
 - Future iterations of the document will generate new versions that will follow the same iteration process; the changes description will be recorded in the first page.

In order to be able to complete the deliverables in due time, it will be necessary to plan the editing of the document carefully, in line with the planning of the corresponding work package. Time for finishing a deliverable depends evidently on its content and purpose. The steps of the approval process are:

Table 3. Quality Assurance Steps

Document version	Action	Who	Time framework
First draft	Circulation to participants in task	Document responsible	At least 15 working days before the deadline
N-th draft...	(This can be repeated depending on the needs and complexity of the deliverable) Comments, suggestions, improvements	Participants in the task	5 working days
Final draft	Circulation to members of the Advisory Board	AB members	5 working days

Final version	Consolidation of comments	Document responsible	2 working days
Submission to EC	Submission to EC	Coordinator	Established deadline

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Table 4. Full list of deliverables

WP No	Del Rel. No	Del No	Title	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Nature	Dissemination Level	Est. Del. Date (annex I)
WP1	D1.1	D1	H - Requirement No. 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants must be submitted as a deliverable. - An analysis of the potential risks to vulnerable individuals/groups that will be involved, and the measures to protect them and minimise the risk of their stigmatisation must be submitted as a deliverable. - Copies of opinions/approvals by ethics committees and/or competent authorities for the research with humans [ethics approvals from institution review boards] must be submitted as a deliverable. 	UDEUSTO	Ethics	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jan 2019
WP1	D1.2	D2	POPD - H - Requirement No. 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The informed consent procedures that will be implemented for the participation of humans and the processing of personal data must be submitted as a deliverable. - Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) must be kept on file. 	UDEUSTO	Ethics	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jan 2019
WP1	D1.3	D3	POPD - Requirement No. 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The host institution must confirm that it has appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research. For host 	UDEUSTO	Ethics	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jan 2019

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				<p>institutions not required to appoint a DPO under the GDPR a detailed data protection policy for the project must be submitted as a deliverable.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data or the equipment used for processing must be submitted as a deliverable. - In case of further processing of previously collected personal data, an explicit confirmation that the beneficiary has legal grounds for the data processing and that the appropriate technical and organisational measures are in place to safeguard the rights of the data subjects must be submitted as a deliverable. 				
WP1	D1.4	D4	GEN - Requirement No. 6	<p>- An independent Ethics Advisor must be appointed to monitor the ethics issues involved in this project and how they are handled. The Advisor must be consulted at least on the following points: human participation including incidental findings policy, risk for stigmatization and relevant safeguards and processing of sensitive personal data, including secondary use. A report by the Ethics Advisor must be submitted with the periodic reports.</p>	UDEUSTO	Ethics	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jan 2019
WP2	D2.1	D5	Project Handbook - m2	<p>Document containing guidelines, management procedures and deadlines to guarantee that the project meets its objectives, proceeds according to schedule, and complies with all the logistic requirements and deliverables as stipulated in the contract.</p>	UDEUSTO	Report	Public	28 Feb 2019

WP2	D2.2	D6	Project Handbook - m44	Document containing guidelines, management procedures and deadlines to guarantee that the project meets its objectives, proceeds according to schedule, and complies with all the logistic requirements and deliverables as stipulated in the contract.	UDEUSTO	Report	Public	31 Aug 2022
WP2	D2.3	D7	Bi-annual Consortium Meeting Report - 1	Document containing the outcomes of the consortium meetings compiled in a report released bi-annually.	UDEUSTO	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	28 Feb 2021
WP2	D2.4	D8	Bi-annual Consortium Meeting Report - 2	Document containing the outcomes of the consortium meetings compiled in a report released bi-annually.	UDEUSTO	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Dec 2022
WP2	D2.5	D9	Data Management Plan and Ethics Handbook - m6	DMP to ensure that data handling and reporting methods are transparent, data is appropriately curated and reusable. This deliverable will include the Ethics Handbook for the project with a table with each WP highlighting if it collects data and if so what and how.	UDEUSTO	ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	30 Jun 2019
WP3	D3.1	D10	Assessment Report	Document containing contextual analysis of legal and cultural practices at the macro level with a sound analysis of the socio-political and normative contexts at the regional and national levels using EU and country-specific reports.	IGOT UL	Report	Public	31 Dec 2019

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WP3	D3.2	D11	Recommendations for GEPs Report	Document containing relevant data on sex segregation, pay gap, work-life balance, and gender discrimination among the GEARING-Roles partners. Data collection will involve surveys and more participatory measures such as focus groups, in-depth interviews, and online forums. Cross-sectional data on age, ethnicity, disability, gender orientation, and religion will also be included.	IGOT UL	Report	Public	31 Dec 2019
WP4	D4.1	D12	Recommendations on how to evolve the OTM-r Toolkit under a gender lenses	Document containing the recommendations to evolve the transparent, merit-based recruitment toolkit (OTM-r toolkit) towards a gender-equality friendly OTM-r toolkit.	FECYT	Report	Public	31 Dec 2020
WP4	D4.2	D13	Reports from the workshops with recommendations for EURAXESS	Document containing the main conclusions from the 2 workshops with recommendations for EURAXESS.	FECYT	Report	Public	30 Jun 2021
WP4	D4.3	D14	Report on the results of the mentoring programme scheme	Document containing the results of the mentoring programme pilot for R2 female researchers.	FECYT	Report	Public	30 Jun 2021
WP4	D4.4	D15	Satisfaction survey for mentors and mentees and report with	Document containing the satisfaction surveys for mentors and mentees and report with results and recommendations on how to set up a successful	FECYT	Report	Public	30 Jun 2021

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			results and recommendations on how to set up a successful mentoring programme for post-doctoral female researchers	mentoring programme for post-doctoral female researchers				
WP5	D5.1	D16	Best Practices Report on Leadership and Decision-Making	Document containing best practices on leadership and decision-making	UDEUSTO	Report	Public	31 Dec 2019
WP5	D5.2	D17	Leadership and Decision-Making Diagnosis Report	Document containing flows of decision-making from senior to middle management in terms of the hiring, recruitment, and promotion decisions as well as the gender representation of decision-makers, depicted as flow charts and an analysis of participative data collection methods.	UDEUSTO	Report	Public	28 Feb 2021
WP5	D5.3	D18	Leadership and Decision-Making Action Plan	Document containing Leadership and Decision-Making Action Plan outlining its recommendations that will then be incorporated in the GEP for each consortium partner.	UDEUSTO	Report	Public	31 Dec 2020
WP5	D5.4	D19	Equality, diversity and inclusion models	Document containing equality, leadership and inclusion modules in training programs.	UDEUSTO	Report	Public	31 Dec 2019

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WP5	D5.5	D20	Report on awareness raising activities	Document containing the outcomes and learnings from equality, leadership and inclusion modules in training programs developed for newly appointed academic leaders and leaders of decision-making bodies and in leadership programs.	UDEUSTO	Report	Public	31 Dec 2019
WP6	D6.1	D21	Incentives scheme proposal for research and innovation	Document containing an incentives scheme that will suggest different forms of rewards or scholarships for researchers who engage with gender-related studies and/or adopt a significant gender perspective in their work.	OBU	Report	Public	31 Dec 2021
WP6	D6.2	D22	Teaching-Learning strategies and activities handbook for GEARING-Roles partners	Document containing the compilation, adaptation, and further development of existing resources providing classroom activity ideas and group management when handling gender-sensitive issues.	OBU	Report	Public	31 Dec 2021
WP6	D6.3	D23	Generic and specific competences relevant to gender mainstreaming	List of generic and specific competencies that will allow teachers to evaluate whether the issue of gender is adequately reflected in their curriculum and assessment.	OBU	Report	Public	31 Dec 2021
WP6	D6.4	D24	Design of gender-sensitive print and online media for awareness	Infographics, photos, and videos to be used in face-to-face and online settings during awareness-raising activities.	OBU	Other	Public	30 Jun 2019

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			raising activities - m6					
WP6	D6.5	D25	Design of gender-sensitive print and online media for awareness raising activities - m12	Infographics, photos, and videos to be used in face-to-face and online settings during awareness-raising activities.	OBU	Other	Public	31 Dec 2019
WP6	D6.6	D26	Design of gender-sensitive print and online media for awareness raising activities - m18	Infographics, photos, and videos to be used in face-to-face and online settings during awareness-raising activities.	OBU	Other	Public	30 Jun 2020
WP6	D6.7	D27	Design of gender-sensitive print and online media for awareness raising activities - m24	Infographics, photos, and videos to be used in face-to-face and online settings during awareness-raising activities.	OBU	Other	Public	31 Dec 2020
WP6	D6.8	D28	Design of gender-sensitive print	Infographics, photos, and videos to be used in face-to-face and online settings during awareness-raising activities.	OBU	Other	Public	30 Jun 2021

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			and online media for awareness raising activities - m30					
WP6	D6.9	D29	Design of gender-sensitive print and online media for awareness raising activities - m36	Infographics, photos, and videos to be used in face-to-face and online settings during awareness-raising activities.	OBU	Other	Public	31 Dec 2021
WP6	D6.10	D30	Task Forces Activity Summary Report	Document containing a summary of the activities carried out by the Task Forces.	OBU	Report	Public	31 Oct 2022
WP7	D7.1	D31	Checklist and instructions for gender training needs assessment	Document containing a checklist and instructions for gender training needs assessments.	Yellow Window	Report	Public	30 Apr 2019
WP7	D7.2	D32	Consolidated training needs assessment	Document containing the consolidated training needs assessment.	Yellow Window	Report	Public	31 Aug 2019
WP7	D7.3	D33	Topical training and train-the-facilitators	Document containing the topical training and train-the-facilitators session concepts and contents.	Yellow Window	Report	Public	31 Dec 2020

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			session concepts and contents - m24					
WP7	D7.4	D34	Compilation of annual working documents on the helpdesk and support function - m48	Document containing the compilation of annual working documents on the helpdesk and support function.	Yellow Window	Other	Public	31 Dec 2022
WP8	D8.1	D35	Dissemination, Communication and Engagement Plan - m3	Dissemination, Communication and Engagement plan to ensure that information on GEARING's activities and tools will be communicated to the appropriate target audiences, at appropriate times, via appropriate methods.	TRI UK	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Mar 2019
WP8	D8.2	D36	Knowledge Sharing Strategy - m6	Document containing the Knowledge Sharing Strategy in order to promote the active participation and engagement among all the consortium partners and to define the strategy to share information using the main channels.	TRI UK	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	30 Jun 2019
WP8	D8.3	D37	Knowledge Sharing Progress Reports	Document containing a summary of learnings, challenges, and effective strategies in engaging with a wider community to be shared with all GEARING-Roles partners and key institutional players in the form of a report.	TRI UK	Report	Public	31 Dec 2022
WP8	D8.4	D38	Open Access Report	Document containing relevant results and information for public dissemination.	TRI UK	Report	Public	31 Dec 2022
WP8	D8.5	D39	Final Dissemination	Document containing the final dissemination and outreach information.	TRI UK	Report	Public	31 Dec 2022

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			and Outreach Report					
WP9	D9.1	D40	Guidelines for GEP design evaluation	Document containing guidelines and processes when evaluating GEARING-Roles partners' GEP implementation, focusing on achieving a coherent and integrated GEP design logic.	RAD	Report	Public	30 Jun 2019
WP9	D9.2	D41	Guidelines for GEP impact evaluation	Document containing a set of guidelines and impact indicators to monitor effectiveness and progress, which will cover the dimensions of effectiveness, efficiency, subjective impact and objective impact.	RAD	Report	Public	30 Jun 2019
WP9	D9.3	D42	GEARING Impact Roadmap	Document containing mechanisms and procedures for impact racking and measurement.	RAD	Report	Public	30 Jun 2019
WP9	D9.4	D43	Annual Impact Evaluation Report - m15	Document containing impact and progress tracking through stakeholder surveys (tool), focus groups, and/or interviews.	RAD	Report	Public	31 Mar 2020
WP9	D9.5	D44	Annual Impact Evaluation Report - m35	Document containing impact and progress tracking through stakeholder surveys (tool), focus groups, and/or interviews.	RAD	Report	Public	30 Nov 2021
WP9	D9.6	D45	Annual Impact Evaluation Report - m47	Document containing impact and progress tracking through stakeholder surveys (tool), focus groups, and/or interviews.	RAD	Report	Public	30 Nov 2022
WP9	D9.7	D46	Final Impact Report	Document containing the indicators achieved, the challenges encountered, and an overall assessment (subjective and objective) of project impact.	RAD	Report	Public	31 Dec 2022

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6. Periodic Reporting

6.1. Reporting Periods

The Gearing Roles Project is divided in three reporting periods:

1st reporting period: January 2019-June 2020

2nd Reporting period: July 2020-December 2021

3rd: Reporting period: January 2022-Dec 2022

6.2. Periodic technical report

With the objective of having a comprehensive view of the progress within each of the WPs, monitoring and progress reporting procedures are established.

For an adequate progress reporting, GEARING Roles uses different kinds of reports:

- *Interim reports (internal)*: Every 6 months, WP Leaders report the progress within the corresponding WP to the Project Coordinator. This report includes a summary of the progress of the corresponding WP and an estimation of the use of resources per partner (provided in this case by the individual partner). A template for the interim report is provided in the Google Drive directory created for the project,
- *Periodic Reports*: at the end of each reporting period, an official period report is submitted to the EC through the ECAS (the European Commission Authentication Service). These reports will be discussed in the review meetings with the EC to evaluate the progress of the project. These reports include a detailed explanation of the progress made during that reporting period as well as the submission of a financial statement for that reporting period. The reports will follow the template provided by the EC.
- *Final Report*: this report will be submitted at end of the project. It will follow the template provided by the EC.

In addition, the Project Coordinator may require a WP leader to report internally on the WP activities at any time during the project lifetime, summarising the status of the execution of the work. Periodic conference calls are organised with the WP Leaders.

6.3. Periodic financial report

Budget and financial related matters must abide with the H2020 Annotated Model Grant Agreement (AMGA) published by the European Commission. In particular, Chapter 3 (art. 5 and 6) of the AMGA refers to the rules that govern the financial matters in H2020 projects. Partners are advised to carefully read the AMGA to ensure that the project is managed correctly and adequately reported from the financial and budgetary point of view.

In case of significant changes in the planned use of resources, partners are advised to inform the Project Coordinator. The PC will then contact the Project Officer to ensure that no issues arise at the time of the reporting and auditing. Likewise, significant changes to the budget and use of resources must be approved by the Gearing Roles Steering Committee.

As already mentioned, GEARING Roles has 3 reporting periods and financial reports have to be submitted by all beneficiaries within 60 days from the end of each reporting period.

DEUSTO as Coordinator will closely monitor and follow up the financial reporting of each beneficiary. The PC will monitor the timely submission of the financial reports to the EC in the form of Financial Statements in the Participant Portal. To this end, the Coordinator will request draft financial reports from

each beneficiary (and linked third party where applicable) within 30 days from the end of the reporting period, to allow sufficient time to check whether there are any significant deviations in the use of resources that should be flagged.

However, each beneficiary remains responsible for its reporting to the EC. Beneficiaries are reminded of the obligation to keep all records and documentation for five years after the payment of the balance (year 2026), according to art. 18 of the GA.

In addition, partners will send an interim report to the PC every 6 months including an estimation of the use of resources. In any event, the PC may require a partner to submit an internal report summarising the use of resources at any time during the project lifetime.

DEUSTO as Project Coordinator will be responsible for the management and redistribution of the funds of the Gearing Roles project, in accordance with the GA and the CA.

As described in the CA, payment schedule, which contains the transfer of pre-financing and interim payments to Parties, will be handled according to the following:

- Funding of costs included in the Consortium Plan will be paid to Parties after receipt from the Funding Authority in separate instalments as agreed below:
- Funding of costs included in the Consortium Plan will be paid to Parties after receipt from the Funding Authority without undue delay and in conformity with the provisions of the Grant Agreement. Costs accepted by the Funding Authority will be paid to the Party concerned. Under no circumstance the Coordinator will respond with its own resources to project payments. All partners will assume subsidiary EC payments delays for incomplete reporting or ineligible expenses. Payments schedule has been designed to ensure the payment to consortium beneficiaries so they can develop all research activities in due time. Payment schedule has been designed as follows:

Table 6. Payments schedule

	Month	% Beneficiary ¹
Prefinancing	1	48%
1 st Interim Payment	20	Amount received in PR1
2 nd Interim Payment	38	Amount received in PR2
Final Payment	48	(5% of the Guarantee Fund + remaining received amount)

7. Risk Management

This management procedure consists on identifying and monitoring, during project implementation, internal and external risks as well as any other issues that might affect the project progress towards its objectives. The purpose is to set up mitigation actions as early as possible. Risks and contingency plans were identified in Part A of Annex I (Critical Risks for Implementation). Each partner has the responsibility to report immediately to their respective WP Leader and to the Project Coordinator any risky situation that may arise and may affect the project objectives or their successful completion. Any change in time

¹ The prefinancing letter the amount to perceive for the whole consortium is 1.449.881,76 Euros, being this 48,33% of the total grant amount. In the C.A. it was stated that the pre-financing payment would be 60% of the maximum grant amount - guarantee fund. This would represent 55% of the maximum grant amount. Being this the case, the payments have been proportionally limited to each partner to the percentage paid by the EC.

schedule of deliverables or in the allocated budget must be reported to the corresponding WP Leader or to the Project Coordinator. In case of problems or delays, the WP leader will be consulted, and it may install task forces to take the necessary actions. In case no resolution is reached, the Gearing Steering Committee will be consulted and will establish mitigation plans to reduce the impact of risk occurring.

Table 7. Risks and mitigation procedures

Description of risk	WPs involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
<p>Resistance from organization against equality measures</p> <p>Probability: Low.</p> <p>Gravity: High</p>	ALL	<p>The design of GEARING-Roles is aimed at counteracting resistance at lower levels through cooperative efforts built on strong support at strategic level in each organization and a participatory methodology ensuring key people in the organization are involved from the start. This support will be sustained thanks to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - close dialogue and involvement of the institutional decision makers and key staff through periodical ad hoc meetings at local and EU level; - inviting key people to joint conferences and meetings with other GEARING-Roles' partners, to discuss concerns and get support in their commitment in promoting female researchers
<p>Lack of support from management in partner institutions.</p> <p>Probability: low, Gravity: high</p>	WP2, WP3 and mainly WP5	Coordinator and WP5 leader will discuss with the team leader of the affected partner whether a discussion at the GSC or a visit at the respective partner organization is appropriate and take action
<p>Disagreement about project implementation among partners</p>	WP2, WP6	Major project goals have been clearly agreed by the partners at the proposal stage, and decision making, and project steering mechanisms will be set up in the final consortium agreement that will be prepared and signed before the formal start of the project. In addition, it will be discussed in GSC meetings. The Advisory Board with its recommendations will serve as an impartial body in disputes on the project implementation.
<p>Tasks take longer time than predicted, causing problems to produce deliverables and increased costs</p> <p>Probability and gravity: medium</p>	WP2- WP7	The work plan will be circulated to all involved staff who will give periodical (every three months) feedback to the WP leaders. Those will periodically inform the scientific coordinator through a form allowing the coordinator to keep close track of progress. If problems cannot be solved by the WP leaders, the coordinator will intervene together with the PMG that will take appropriate actions. This might lead to termination of a partner's participation after communication with the EC Project Officer.
<p>Withdrawal of a consortium</p>	All WPs	Every partner within the consortium offers the project its own unique expertise and all members have obtained full support of the highest management level. If partner needs to leave the consortium, the PMT will do any possible effort to

member, loss of a key expert Probability: low Gravity: medium		replace them with a partner with equal expertise or to smoothly distribute the work to other partners.
Poor communication between partners and lack of engagement of stakeholder for the different work packages	WP2, WP7	A whole range of communication tools will be used to avoid communication problems, including face to face meetings, online conference calls, social media. In addition, the project coordinator will be active in maintaining and stimulating proper communication between partners. The project coordinator together with work package leaders will monitor stakeholder participation

8. Additional information

This deliverable has explained the management procedures to be used in GEARING ROLES project. It has dealt with how progress will be monitored and controlled, risks controlled, financial reporting and associated payment executed, insurance of the highest possible quality for deliverables and internal project communication. The spreadsheets supporting this deliverable will continuously be updated during the project execution. This deliverable will also be updated regularly, at least every 6 months

9. Contact Information

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She holds a degree in Law from the University of Deusto and a PhD in Human Rights earned at the same University. She has a solid background in research, both in scientific production and in the management of research and the dynamization of teams, as well as teaching experience in the Faculty of Law of the UPV-EHU. Currently she works as a researcher at the Deusto vice rectorate for identity and mission where she coordinates the H2020 project Gearing Roles aimed at implementing 6 Gender Equality Plans in 6 European Research organisations. The focus of her research is on the conflict in Western Sahara, which has addressed from different perspectives such as Local

Human Development or gender equality, but mainly from the perspective of human rights, specifically from the rights of victims of forced disappearance, and transitional justice.

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She is PhD in Political Science and Sociology at University of Deusto. She is Professor in the Social and Human Sciences Faculty of University of Deusto (Bilbao, Spain). Principle Researcher of DeustoSocialValues Research Team that represents Spain in the EuropeanValuesSystemGroup (EVS). She is a member of the Executive Committee of the EVS <http://www.europeanvaluesstudy.eu/page/executive-committee.html>

She has been Dean of the Political Science and Sociology Faculty (2004-2009) and Director of the Master in intervention against women violence (2003-2009). She

has been President of the Basque Association of Sociology (AVSP) and Vice-President of the Spanish Federation of Sociology (FES). She has been Director of the Basque Institute of Woman - Emakunde of the Basque Government (2009-2012)

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She is associate professor in the Department of Modern Languages, where she teaches graduate and undergraduate courses in Gender Studies, English Literature, and European and Cultural Studies. She also taught at the University of the Basque Country, and at Santa Clara University (USA). She has been a postdoctoral

Fulbright fellow at Stanford University, Department of English, (2008-2009), and at the Folger Shakespeare Library, USA (2007). She has published on Literature and Gender in the Early-Modern period and in Women and the Media. Currently she is Deputy Director of International Relations at the University of Deusto, Bilbao, where she formerly held administrative positions as Director of Graduate Studies (2009-2015) and Vice-Dean at the Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities (2012-2015).

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Leire Gartzia, Ph.D., is professor of Leadership and Change Management at Deusto Business School. She earned a joint European Ph.D. in organizational psychology at the University of the Basque Country and the Rotterdam School of Management, and in 2011 she completed a postdoctoral fellowship at Northwestern University, US. She has been a visiting researcher at several universities and Business Schools, resulting in relevant publications about gender issues in management in business journals like Group and Organization Management, Journal of Business Research, or the

European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology. Her research also includes publications in relevant gender sources like The Oxford Handbook of Gender in Organizations or the participation as Guest Editor in the journal Sex Roles, developing a Special Issue about Gender Research in Spain. Her gender research has been recognized by relevant international awards including the Academy of Management Best Paper and the Dorothy Harlow distinction in Gender Studies. Next to her academic activities, Dr. Gartzia has combined research with the business world, giving lectures and courses about organizational behavior and leadership from a gender perspective to employees and managers.

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Dolores Morondo Taramundi is Head of Research at the Human Rights Institute of the University of Deusto. She studied in Deusto, Oñati and Brussels and holds a PhD from the European University Institute. Until 2011 she taught Legal Philosophy and History and Philosophy of Human Rights at the University of Urbino (Italy). Since her arrival at Deusto she has participated in several research projects, including large-scale European projects (FRAME, INTEGRIM). She teaches International Protection and Promotion of Human Rights for undergrads and Human Rights Research Methodology in postgraduate programmes. Her research focuses mainly on human rights, antidiscrimination law, critical legal theories, especially feminist legal theory, legal argumentation, text and (critical) discourses analysis. She has worked as an independent expert for the European Commission and for the Spanish Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

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Antonia Caro González, Head of the International Research Project Office at the University of Deusto, has sound experience in managing complex interdisciplinary research collaborations and community engagement with multi-stakeholder counterparts (academic, government, private sector and civil society). With over 20 years of experience in research internationalisation, Antonia is the senior counsellor for the Rector team in strategic research planning. She is currently responsible of the three Deusto

Master Plans on “Internationalisation”, “Social Impact” and “Interdisciplinary Platforms”) and in charge of boosting the 6 I’s Research Model and its implementation at the University of Deusto.

She is evaluator for the European Commission (H2020, Cosme), manager and researcher in international research projects (FP7-GEITONIES; FP7-SPBUILD; FP7-INTEGRIM; FP7-SI-DRIVE, H2020-SOLIDUS, H2020-DIRS COFUND, H2020-GEARING Roles).

Dr Caro is member of various Board of Directors: European Social Innovation School (ESSI); the “Covenant on Demographic Change” and of the Ethics, Disciplinary and Private Relations Committee of

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She obtained her Ph.D. degree in Romance Languages and Literatures at Harvard University (Cambridge, USA). Until 2002 she was a professor in the departments of Spanish, Comparative Literature and Women’s Studies at Columbia University (New York, USA), and presently she teaches at the Department of Communication at University of Deusto in San Sebastian. She has published six books and fifty articles and book chapters on literature, film, culture and gender studies, and is the winner of three national essay prizes. She is the Principal Researcher of the research group Communication at Deusto University. She has been awarded three research sexenios by the CNEAI (National Assessment Commission on Research Activities). She is a member of the editorial board of several academic journals and has recently been a Visiting Professor at the University of Dartmouth College (2013), University of Chicago (2015), and Columbia University (2016). Her last book, written with Rob Stone is titled *Basque Cinema: A Cultural and Political History* (London, IB Tauris, 2016).

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Ph.D. in Philosophy, she is presently researcher of the Pedro Arrupe Human Rights Institute and professor in the Department of International Relations and Humanities at the University of Deusto, where she teaches graduate and undergraduate courses in Ancient Philosophy, Critical Thinking, Contemporary Critical Theories and Research Ethics. Her main research field is political philosophy with an emphasis on issues related to critical theories. She has participated in numerous investigations on the role of different social actors, mainly companies, universities and social organizations in contexts of social vulnerability, in particular in relation with the protection of the human

rights. She has been a visiting scholar in numerous European and American universities. She has written and edited 15 books and more than a hundred articles and book chapters on political philosophy and applied ethics. She is currently working on epistemology and methodology in Human Rights and she is the coordinator of the research ethics board at the University of Deusto.

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He has been a Researcher is at the DeustoTech-Computing research unit since 2008. He received his PhD from the PhD in Information Systems with full marks cum laude in 2012 in the topic of malware detection in Android mobile devices. His main research skills and interest include machine learning, big data, knowledge discovery and information retrieval. He has a long track-record

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Lorena Fernández Álvarez. I'm the director of digital identity at the University of Deusto, in Spain. I also work promoting scientific and technological vocations of girls and women. For example, I'm part of the Ada Byron Prize to Women Technologist team and the Inspira STEAM mentoring program. I'm member of the EC "Gendered Innovations 2" Expert Group.

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B.Sc. Computer Engineering (2007), University of Deusto. Master's Degree on Information Security (2010), University of Deusto. Ph.D. on Information systems (2013) with the maximum qualification and with honours, University of Deusto. Big Data and Business Intelligence Programme (2015), University of Deusto. Research experience: Machine Learning Methods, Computer Vision, Optimization of Processes and Big Data. Previous EU projects: IPRO (EUROSTARS, 2010-2013), DANTE (H2020, 2016-2019).

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migration, mobilities and urban transformation and migration, demographic change and regional development. She is a member of the Board of Directors and of the Executive Board of IMISCOE research network and of the International Steering Committee of the Metropolis International Project. She participated in several international EU funded and national research projects in the fields of international migration and integration and has wide experience in post-graduate research training. Currently, in addition to GEARING ROLES, she participates in the project P- RIDE – Portugal: Regional integration of Demography and Economy (funded by FCT – The National Foundation for Science and Technology) and is the team leader at CEG/IGOT of two international projects : i) Cross-Migration (H2020-SC6-REV-INEQUAL-2017, Coordination and support action) and MEHR MEHR - Modernisation, Education and Human Rights. ERASMUS +, Cooperation for Innovation and the Exchange of Good Practices, Strategic Partnerships for higher education (2016-2019). Recently, she co-edited with C. Timmerman, L. van Van Praag and S. Pereira (2018). Gender and migration. A gender sensitive-approach to migration dynamics. Leuven: Leuven University Press.

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She has a PhD in Human Geography from the University of Lisbon. She is Associate Professor at the Institute of Geography and Spatial Planning (IGOT) and a researcher at the Centre for Geographical Studies (CEG), of the University of Lisbon. She is the editor in chief of the journal 'Finisterra – Revista Portuguesa de Geografia' and a founding member of the REGGSILA Network ('Studies of Ibero-Latin American Geography, Gender and Sexuality': REGGSILA – Rede de Estudos de Geografia, Género e Sexualidades Ibero Latino-americana).

Research and teaching topics have focused on gender, environment and spatial planning. She has collaborated in several (national and international) projects: 'National Programme for Spatial Planning Policy' (PNPOT); 'Spatial Plan for the West and Tagus Valley Region (PROT OVT)'; 'Gender indicators for environment and territory' and 'Gender Mainstreaming Guide'; 'Policies and Measures to promote Gender Equality in Municipalities'; 'Study to support the implementation of national equality policy measures from a territorial perspective'. 'GenMob, Gender and Mobility: inequality in spacetime' (EEA Grants, PT07, 2nd Open Call); Gender Equality Actions in Research Institutions to traNsform Gender ROLES (GEARING-Roles project - H2020-SwafS-2018-20 Type of action: CSA). She regularly advises municipal councils for the implementation of municipal and intermunicipal plans for gender equality.

Alina Esteves

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holds a PhD in Human Geography from the University of Lisbon (2005). She is currently Auxiliar Professor of Human Geography at the Institute of Geography and Spatial Planning (IGOT), University of Lisbon, and researcher at the Unit MIGRARE - Migration, Spaces and Societies at the Centre for Geographical Studies (CEG).

She has been working in the areas of migration studies, with a particular focus on labour market, portability of welfare rights, and human rights as learning outcomes in Higher Education in Portugal.

Jennifer McGarrigle

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holds a PhD in Urban Studies from the University of Glasgow, UK. She is currently Assistant Professor of Human Geography in the Institute of Geography and Spatial Planning (IGOT) and researcher in the Centre for Geographical Studies, at the University of Lisbon. Her research interests lie at the intersection of migration and urban studies. She has conducted extensive research on residential processes, housing and religious minorities in the UK and Portugal. Her current research focuses on new forms of international residential mobility and impacts in urban areas, with a particular focus on investment and lifestyle migration. She is author of "Understanding Processes of Ethnic Concentration and Dispersal"

(University of Amsterdam Press, 2010) and has published in various journals such as the Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies, Housing Studies, Finisterra, Social Inclusion and Tourism Geographies.

Milica Antič Gaber

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Milica Antič Gaber is Senior Researcher and Full Professor at the Department of Sociology at Faculty of Arts, University of Ljubljana, where she teaches Sociology of Gender at graduate and post-graduate level and coordinates Doctoral program on Gender Studies. She was a visiting scholar and lecturer at Central European University in Budapest, Centre for Women's Studies in Belgrade, Inter-University Centre in Dubrovnik, Birkbeck College in London, Centre for Women's Studies in Novi Sad and University of Pompeu Fabra in Barcelona. She participated in or coordinated national and international projects on gender equality, including European Commission's (Daphne II) project Ways of Implementing European Directives on Violence against Women, Children and Youth: Good practices and recommendations (2006-

2009); Balancing private and professional life as an obstacle to the greater presence of women in politics (2008-2012); Gender Structure of Slovene Society and the Position of Genders in Politics (2012-2014) and international project The Electoral Gender Quota Systems and their Implementations in Europe (2011, 2013). She is a member of the Expert Council for Gender Equality at the Slovene Ministry of Labour, and was a member of the Expert Forum of European Institute for Gender Equality. She was a Head of Slovene Sociological Association (2010-2016) and is currently a member of Executive Board of European Sociological Association.

Univerza v Ljubljani

Živa Kos

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Živa Kos is Researcher at Faculty of Arts UL and collaborator at CEPS (Center for Educational Policy) at Faculty of Education UL. She obtained her PhD in Educational policy at Faculty of Education, University of Ljubljana. She was a member of an Expert Consultant Group for Quality Assurance Agency for Education in 2015 and part of the preparatory group for guidelines for Education Strategic Framework 2016-2030 at Ministry of Education of Slovenia. She was Expert Researcher in national and international projects, including Vocational Assessor Requirements in Europe (2016), How Initial Teacher Education prepares student teachers to deal with

diversity in the classroom (2016) and Neoliberalism in the European Higher Education Area: Between the Efficiency and Equity of Slovenian Education Policies and Practices ; education, efficiency, equity, education, European educational space (2017). She is a member of Slovene Sociological Association

Univerza v Ljubljani

Tjaša Cankar

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Tjaša Cankar B.A (History and Sociology), is currently finishing Master's degree at the Department of Sociology at Faculty of Arts, University of Ljubljana. She's academically interested in feminist political theory, critical social theory and geopolitical economy. She is a member of Slovenian NGO Gender Equality Research Institute, where her goals revolve around improving gender equality and promoting women's leadership and political participation.

Univerza v Ljubljani

Jasna Podreka

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Jasna Podreka is Researcher and Teacher Assistant at the Department of Sociology at Faculty of Arts, University of Ljubljana. She obtained her PhD in 2014, defending thesis on gender-based killings of women by male intimate partners. She was a member of the European Cooperation in Science & Technology Action IS1206 Femicide across Europe for the period 2013-2017. Besides gender-based violence and femicide, her main research interests are discrimination and inequalities in fields of work, politics and personal life. She is a member of Slovene Sociological Association and is actively engaged in Association SOS Helpline for Women and Children who were victims of

violence.

She is also a guest lecturer at educational panels on gender-based violence for police force, social workers and members of NGOs.

Anne Laure Humbert

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She is a Reader and Director of the Centre for Diversity Policy Research and Practice at Oxford Brookes University. She has developed a range of ways to measure gender and diversity, and has also designed and delivered various gender-related training programmes. Anne will lead the Oxford Brookes team, and in particular will oversee the delivery of Work Package 6 which includes the development of gender-sensitive resources and guidelines for teaching and learning strategies, and assessment of gender-related competencies

Kate Clayton-Hathway

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She is a Research Fellow with the Centre for Diversity Policy Research and Practice in Oxford Brookes Business School. As an interdisciplinary social scientist, Kate has a long-standing interest in gender equality issues and is an experienced qualitative researcher and lecturer. Kate will be working closely with Dr Humbert to liaise with project partners and support all aspects of delivery. In particular, she will support delivery of Work Package 6 through development of training materials plus organising and promoting community Sengagement activities.

Simonetta Manfredi

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She is Associate Dean for Research and Knowledge Exchange for Oxford Brookes Business School. Her research area is equality and diversity issues in the workplace with a focus on applied diversity policy research in higher education. Simonetta will be providing high-level expertise to the OBU team in delivery Work Package 6, in addition to liaising with, and initiating engagement with, senior colleagues to facilitate shared learning.

Ayşe Gül Altınay

altinay@sabanciuniv.edu

Ayşe Gül is responsible for developing and maintaining the relations with stakeholders of the project at the university and national level. She oversees the overall running of the project and is directly involved with both the analysis and the action implementation components of the project.

Zeynep Gülru Göker

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Gülru is responsible for general coordination of the project and maintaining the inter-consortium communication. She manages the analysis and implementation components and also oversees the dissemination activities of the

project

İlayda Ece Ova

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İlayda is responsible for managing the social media accounts of the project, as well as conducting literature review and data gathering (of existing data at the national level). She also supports the implementation and analysis activities

Kadri Raudvere

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Taking care the project was launched and and all tasks Estonian Research Council is responsible for carried out (its general organisational tasks within all WP-s, communication with stakeholders within and outside the organisation)

Eesti Teadusagentuur
Estonian Research Council

Karin Jaanson

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She holds a MPA from University of Georgia and MA in economics from the University of Tartu and BA from Tallinn Technical Universtiy. She has been working on different managerial positions in government sector e.g. been vice mayor of Tartu City Government as well as Elva City Government. She has also experinedced in the research policy management as she has been a Councilor at the Ministry of Education and Research and Councilor for Vice Rector for Research at University of Tartu. Since 2015 she has been workng as an Executive Director of Estonian Research Council.

Eesti Teadusagentuur
Estonian Research Council

Anne Park

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Taking care of the financial side of the project.

Eesti Teadusagentuur
Estonian Research Council

Maarja Sillaste

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She holds a degree in government and politics from the University of Tartu. Before starting at the Estonian Research Council in 2012 she has been gathering experiences from the Tallinn University and Estonian University of Life Sciences on different administrative positions as well as lecturer. Starting in 2012 at the Estonian Research Council as a research funding officer she fastly advanced to further positions and from 2018 has been the Head of the Department of R&D Analysis.

Eesti Teadusagentuur
Estonian Research Council

Lut Mergaert

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Lut is Belgian, holds a PhD in Management Sciences (2012, Radboud University Nijmegen; dissertation entitled 'The Reality of Gender Mainstreaming Implementation – the Case of the EU Research Policy'), a MSc. degree in Applied Economics and obtained a Certificate of Women's Studies. Lut has over 20 years' experience managing pan-European studies of which many for the European Commission, is an experienced qualitative social researcher, evaluation specialist (member of the European Evaluation Society) and a gender consultant. She has been the project leader in a significant number of policy support studies, in which position she facilitated numerous focus group discussions, consultations,

(online) forums, etc. She was project leader and/or author of several assignments for the European Commission, including "Monitoring progress towards Gender Equality in the Sixth Framework Programme – Science and Society" and "Gender in EU-funded Research – Toolkit and Training" (DG RTD, 2009-2010 and 2011-2012), and for the European Institute for Gender Equality, coordinating studies covering all EU Member States. She authored many reports, academic articles and book chapters on the subject of gender equality in research and science. Lut was Management Committee member for Belgium and co-leader of Work Group 2 – Task Force on Gender in Research and Innovation for the COST-funded action GenderSTE (Gender in Science, Technology, Environment). Upon the request of the European Commission, she was a Member of the Advisory Board of the EU-funded project 'Responsible Research and Innovation: Tools and Training' to represent gender equality expertise on that Board. She is fluent in English and Dutch and has working knowledge of French.

YELLOW WINDOW

Alain Denis

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Alain is Belgian and holds a MSc in Applied Economics. He is an expert in decision-support studies and has been project director, senior consultant or trainer in numerous pan-European or international projects, focusing or covering gender equality topics. Alain advises various bodies as evaluation and public health specialist. Alain is fluent in English, French and Dutch and has working knowledge of German, Portuguese and Spanish.

YELLOW WINDOW

Katrien Van der Heyden

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YELLOW WINDOW

Maxime Forest

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Maxime, French, is a senior researcher and policy analyst at Sciences Po-OFCE and associate researcher at Sciences Po-CEVIPOF. His research interests focus on gender equality policies in a comparative perspective, intersecting inequalities, and organizational changes to achieve gender equality - primarily in research and the academia, and women's access to decision-making. Since 2014, he has been Scientific Coordinator of the EU-funded EGERA project (FP7, 2014-2017), involving RPOs in the EU and Turkey. He has published as main author or co-editor numerous books, as well as book chapters and articles in national and international peer-reviewed journals. He is also the author of a dozen of research and evaluation

reports on gender mainstreaming instruments and gender equality policies for the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), the European Commission (DG JUST, DG Research), the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research, the Council of Europe and the French Council of the Judiciary. He has been recently involved in the comparative analysis of policies to integrate gender in RPOs commissioned by EIGE. Since 2012, he has collaborated with Yellow Window both as a researcher and a gender trainer in the field of research and innovation. Appointed as executive member of the French High Gender Council in 2013 and 2016, he is also a deputy member of the Gender Equality advisory body of DG JUST, and an international jury member of the UNESCO prize for girls and women's education.

YELLOW WINDOW

Izaskun Lakunza

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She is the International Projects head of unit in FECYT since 2014. She is responsible for the participation of FECYT in European projects related to researcher mobility and researchers career development. The unit also coordinates the institutional relations with the

Associations of Spanish Researchers in different countries and cooperates with the Spanish Embassies in S&T matters. From 2012 to 2014 she was the Executive Director of the Association of European Research Libraries (LIBER). She holds a PhD in Chemistry.

Xabier Eekhout

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He is a project manager within the International Project unit of FECYT. After working as a junior researcher in the Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, a research centre of the Spanish Research Council (CSIC), he specialized in EU project management. In October 2011 he was hired by FECYT to coordinate the FP7 project EURAXESS TOP II (January 2012 – December 2014). Since October 2015 he is back in FECYT to manage its participation in other EURAXESS-related European projects (EURAXIND, TOP III, EUESCADA, etc.). Apart from EU projects, he also collaborates in the management of the EURAXESS Spain network coordinated by FECYT, and has participated in

several working groups related to researcher career development.

Gustavo García Turiño

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He holds a degree in Law and Business Administration and a Master's degree in Auditory. He worked for twelve years in the Financial Department of State owned foundations Genoma España and FECYT, both of them dedicated to promoting science and innovation in Spain. From 2009 to 2012 he was the Head of the Financial Department of Genoma España and from 2013 to 2018 he was the Head of the Financial Unit in FECYT. In this position he was in charge of accounting, forecasting and

budgeting among other tasks. Since July 2018 he works in the International Projects Area of FECYT, in charge of the legal and financial aspects of these projects.

Julia Murasziewicz

Project Lead

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She will supervise all dissemination and outreach activities and lead Trilateral's administrative responsibilities.

Olivia Iannelli

Project Officer

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She will be the main contact for dissemination and outreach activities, she will lead and coordinate campaigns, videos, podcasts, communication strategy and evaluation

Angelo Napolano

Project Supervisor & Support

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His activities will include supervision and coordination, while supporting various on Dissemination and Outreach Activities

Francesca Kuhanuka

Project Assistant

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Project Assistant, Social Media and other Dissemination activities (including campaigns, videos, podcasts and strategy).

TRILATERAL
RESEARCH

Ekaterina Kyulyumova

Graphic Designer

Kate will undertake all the design work for this project.

TRILATERAL
RESEARCH

Mieke Verloo

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Professor Mieke Verloo is an expert in the fields of gender and politics. Mieke Verloo is Professor of Comparative Politics and Inequality Issues at Radboud University in the Netherlands, and Non-Residential Permanent Fellow at the IWM, Institute for Human Sciences in Vienna. She is the winner of the 2015 ECPG Gender and Politics Career Achievement Award. She was scientific director of large research projects on gender equality policymaking in Europe (see www.mageeq.net and www.quing.eu). She has extensive consultancy and training experience on

gender mainstreaming and intersectionality for several European governments and institutions. Her current research is on feminist politics and opposition to gender+ equality in Europe.

Radboud University

Inge Bleijbergh

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Inge Bleijbergh is an expert in participatory research, facilitated modeling, gender & decision-making and social policies. She finished her PhD on European social citizenship at the Vrije Universiteit in Amsterdam in 2004 and moved to Radboud University in 2006. She started to model social policy and diversity to involve decision makers in analyzing and addressing complex problems.

Radboud University

ANNEXES

The EU Framework Programme
for Research and Innovation

HORIZON 2020

ANNEX 1: TEMPLATE OF PERIODIC REPORT

H2020 Programme

Periodic Report Template (RIA, IA, CSA,
SME instrument, MSCA)

Periodic Technical Report (parts A and B)
Periodic Financial Report

Version 2.1
19 December 2017

Disclaimer

This document is aimed at informing potential applicants for Horizon 2020 funding. It serves only as an example. The actual Web forms and templates, provided in the online reporting system under the Participant Portal, might differ from this example. Periodic and final reports must be prepared and submitted via the online reporting system under the Participant Portal.

Structure of the Periodic Report

The periodic report must be submitted by the coordinator within 60 days following the end of each reporting period. It contains the periodic technical and financial reports.

The **periodic technical report** consists of two parts:

- **Part A** of the periodic technical report contains the cover page, a publishable summary and the answers to the questionnaire covering issues related to the project implementation and the economic and social impact, notably in the context of the Horizon 2020 key performance indicators and the Horizon 2020 monitoring requirements. **Part A is generated by the IT system. It is based on the information entered by the participants through the periodic report and continuous reporting modules of the electronic exchange system in the Participant Portal.** The participants can update the information in the continuous reporting module at any time during the life of the project.
- **Part B** of the periodic technical report is the narrative part that includes explanations of the work carried out by the beneficiaries during the reporting period. Part B needs to be uploaded as a PDF document following the template of Part B Periodic Technical report.

The **periodic financial report** consists of:

- Individual financial statements (Annex 4 to the GA) for each beneficiary;
- Explanation of the use of resources and the information on subcontracting and in-kind contributions provided by third parties from each beneficiary for the reporting period concerned;
- A periodic summary financial statement including the request for interim payment.

Preparation and submission of periodic report

- **Continuous reporting functionality** in the participant portal: it is activated at the time the project starts and it is continuously open for the beneficiaries to submit deliverables, to report on progress in achieving milestones, to follow up of critical risks, ethics issues, publications, communications activities, and the answers to the questionnaire on horizontal issues.

- **Periodic reporting functionality in the participant portal:** following the end of each reporting period the functionality of periodic reporting in the Participant Portal will be activated. While the periodic reporting session is open in the electronic exchange system:

- each participant will be able to complete on-line their own Financial Statement (and the financial report of their Third Parties, if any) including the explanations on the use of resources;
- coordinator will be able to upload the Part B of the periodic technical report as a pdf document.

When the coordinator submits the periodic report, the IT tool will capture the information from the continuous reporting module in order to generate the Part A of the periodic technical report. The IT tool will consolidate the individual financial statements and it will generate automatically the report with explanations of the use of resources and the periodic summary financial statements, which corresponds to the request for payment.

The periodic technical report will be 'locked for review' by the coordinator before its submission. Make sure the information in the continuous reporting module is up-to-date before the periodic report is 'locked for review'. Updates entered after this step will be included in the periodic report of the following period.

- Instructions and footnotes in blue will not appear in the text generated by the IT system.
- For options [in square brackets]: the option that applies must be chosen in the IT system. Options not chosen will automatically either not appear or appear as 'not applicable'.
- For fields in [grey in square brackets] (even if they are part of an option as specified in the previous item): enter the appropriate data in the IT system.
- Data in coloured fields will be prefilled by the IT tool.

PERIODIC REPORT

Grant Agreement number:	[insert Grant Agreement number]
Project² Acronym:	[insert acronym]
Project title:	[insert project title]
Start date of the project:	[insert dd/mm/yyyy]
Duration of the project:	[insert duration in months]
<i>[Option for MSCA Supervisor name:</i>	[insert name] /
<i>[Option for MSCA Researcher name:</i>	[insert name] /
Period covered by the report:	from [insert dd/mm/yyyy] to [insert dd/mm/yyyy]
Periodic report:	[1 st] [2 nd] [3 rd] [4] rd
Date of submission of the periodic report:	[insert dd/mm/yyyy]
Version:	[insert number]
Project website² address:	[insert website address]
The report is elaborated on the basis of the:	- Original Grant agreement - Amended Grant Agreement through amendment n° [insert number]

(*)Table is completed automatically

² The term 'project' used in this template equates to an 'action' in certain other Horizon 2020 documentation ²
The home page of the website should contain the European flag which are available in electronic format at the Europa website (European flag: http://europa.eu/abc/symbols/emblem/index_en.htm) and the Horizon 2020 programme name.

1. Summary for publication

This section is structured in three sub-sections that must be completed on-line with suitable quality to enable direct publication by the Commission/Agency. It should be easy to read i.e. written in a language easily understandable by a broader public, thereby promoting the dissemination and supporting the exploitation of EU funded results. It should preferably not exceed 7480 characters (equivalent to two pages of a text document). This part must not contain any confidential data.

The summary for publication must be drafted as a "stand-alone" text. No references should be made to other parts of the report. References can be made only to publicly available information.

Beside the summary filled within the tool, diagrams or photographs illustrating and promoting the work of the project can be provided (only as images)³.

1.1 Summary of the context and overall objectives of the project

This section must be completed on-line (see above).

1.2 Work performed from the beginning of the project to the end of the period covered by the report and main results achieved so far

This section must be completed on-line (see above).

1.3 Progress beyond the state of the art, expected results until the end of the project and potential impacts (including the socio-economic impact and the wider societal implications of the project so far)

This section must be completed on-line (see above).

³ Any rights of third parties must be cleared in advance in accordance with the GA.

2. Deliverables

Del. no.	Deliverable name	WP no.	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemin. level	Delivery date from Annex 1	Actual delivery date	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date if appropriate	Status	Comments
[insert deliverable number]	[insert deliverable name]	[insert WP number]	[insert beneficiary short name]	[R] [DEM] [DEC] [OTHER]	[PU] [CO] [CI]	[insert month number]	[insert dd/mm/yyyy]	[insert dd/mm/yyyy]	[Not submitted] [Request for revision] [Not assessed yet] [Not valid] [Accepted]	[insert comments]

Milest. no.	Milestone title	Related WP(s) no.	Lead beneficiary	Delivery date from Annex 1	Means of verification	Achieved	If not achieved Forecast achievement date	Comments
[insert MS number]	[insert milestone name]	[insert WP number]	[insert beneficiary short name]	[insert dd/mm/yyyy]	[insert means of verification as in Annex 1]	[YES] [NO]	[insert dd/mm/yyyy]	[insert comment if needed]

Ethic deliverables	Due date of the compliance of the ethic deliverables	Report of the independent ethics advisor/ advisory board if applicable	Comments
[insert requirement as in Annex I]	[insert dd/mm/yyyy]	[Not submitted] [Submitted]	[insert comment]

(*) Data in coloured fields will be prefilled by the IT tool.

3. Milestones

(*) Data in coloured fields will be prefilled by the IT tool.

4. Ethical Issues (if applicable)

(*) Data in coloured fields will be prefilled by the IT tool.

5. Critical implementation risks and mitigation actions

At the end of each period beneficiaries should give the state of play of every risk identified in Annex 1 and if necessary give new mitigation measures.

Foreseen Risks

The following table lists the Risks identified in Annex 1. The table is read-only and it is provided as a reference for the State of Play table below.

Risk Number	Description of Risk	Work Packages Concerned	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
insert risk number as in Annex 1 []	insert risk description as in Annex 1 []	insert WP number []	insert mitigation measure as in Annex 1 []

(*) Data in coloured fields will be prefilled by the IT tool.

Unforeseen Risks

Risk Number	Description of Risk	Work Packages Concerned	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
[inumber foreseen risk]	[insert risk description]	[insert WP number]	[insert mitigation measure]

States of the Play for Risk Mitigation

Risk Number	Period	Did you apply risk mitigation measures?	Did your risk materialise?	Comments
[risk number]	[periinumber]	[YES] [NO]	[YES] [NO]	[insert comment if needed; mandatory if the risk mitigation measures have not been applied]

6. Dissemination and exploitation of results 6.1 Scientific publications

Publications accessible via OpenAIRE will be displayed automatically. Beneficiaries will only need to check if the publications are linked to the project.

In case of publications not registered via OpenAIRE, the beneficiary encodes the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and all the rest of information is complete automatically.

Type of scientific publication	Title of the scientific publication	DOI	ISSN or eSSN	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent	Number, date	Publisher	Place of publication	Year of publication	Relevant pages	Public & private publication ³	Peerreview	Is/Will open access provided to this publication
[Article in journal] [Publication in conference proceeding/workshop] [Books/Monographs] [Chapters in books] [Thesis/dissertation]	insert title of the publication	insert DOI reference	[insert ISSN or eSSN number]	[insert authors' name(s)]	insert title of the journal	[insert number of the journal] [insert month of the publication] [insert year of the publication]		[insert place of publication]	insert year of the publication	[insert first page of the publication] [insert last page of the publication]	[YES] [NO]	[YES] [NO]	[Yes - Green OA [insert the length of embargo if any]] [Yes - Gold OA [insert the amount of processing charges in EUR if any]] [NO]

(*) Data to be completed only if DOI not available.

³ Both the joint publications coming from academic and corporate project participants as well as joint publications of project participants with academic/corporate organisations outside the consortium (as long as they are related to the funded project) should be reported.

6

.2 Dissemination and communication activities

List only activities directly linked to the project.

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Number
[Organisation of a Conference] [Organisation of a workshop] [Press release] [Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)] [Exhibition] [Flyers] [Training] [Social media] [Web-site] [Communication campaign (e.g radio, TV)] [Participation to a conference] [Participation to a workshop] [Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop] [Video/film] [Brokerage event] [Pitch event] [Trade fair] [Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)] [Other]	[insert number of activities]
Total funding amount	[insert amount in EUR]

(*) One row per type of activity selected from the drop-down menu in the IT tool.

Type of audience reached In the context of all dissemination & communication activities (multiple choices! is possible)	Estimated Number of persons reached
[Scientific Community (higher education, Research)] [Industry] [Civil Society] [General Public] [Policy makers] [Medias] [Investors] [Customers] [Other]	[insert number]

(*) One row per type of activity selected from the drop-down menu in the IT tool.

.3 Intellectual property rights resulting from the project

Type of IP Rights	Application reference	Date of the application	Official title of the application	Applicant(s)	Has the IPR protection been awarded?	If available, official publication number of award of protection
[Patent] [Trademark] [Registered design] [Utility model] [Other]	<p><i>[Option for international applications of patents [insert IP international organisation code] [insert serial number]]</i></p> <p><i>[Option for national applications of patents [insert country code (two letters)] [insert serial number]]</i></p> <p><i>[Option for other registered IPR [insert application reference country code (two letters) or organisation code] [insert alphanumeric identifier]]</i></p>	[insert dd/mm/yyyy]	[insert title of the application]	[insert beneficiary(ies) name]	[YES] [NO] [No applicable]	<p><i>[Option for patents [insert code (two letters referring to a country or organisation)] [insert serial number]]</i></p> <p><i>[Option for rest [insert official publication number]]</i></p>

(*) By encoding the application reference part of the data will be automatically completed.

.4 Innovation

Explanation on the terminology used can be found in the Online Manual.

7. Impact on SMEs

[Option for all projects with an SME]

SME Name	Turnover of the company at the beginning of the project/most recent accountability period from the beginning of the project	Number of employees at the beginning of the project/ most recent accountability period from the beginning of the project	Turnover of the company at the most recent accountability period	Number of employees at the most recent accountability period
[insert name of SME]	[insert amount from database (pre-filled if information is available, otherwise the user will need to enter the information manually)]	[insert amount from database (pre-filled if information is available, otherwise the user will need to enter the information manually)]	[insert amount]	[insert number]

(*) Data in coloured fields will be prefilled by the IT tool.

[Option for SME Instrument only]

Please fill in the table with your estimated forecasts for turnover and employment for the next 3 years (for the multi-beneficiaries project the coordinator should provide figures for the whole project consortium).

	1 year after project completion	2 years after project completion	3 years after project completion
Turnover (€)	[insert amount]	[insert amount]	[insert amount]
Employment (Headcounts)	[insert number]	[insert number]	[insert number]

[Option mandatory for all projects not opting out of the extended 'Open research data pilot' (now covering all of Horizon 2020)]

8. Open Research Data

More information on Data Management Plans (DMPs) in the Online Manual.

Digital Object Identifier, DOI (if available)	Title/Identifier (if no DOI available)	Is this dataset Openly accessible ⁵ ?	Is this dataset reusable ⁶	If the dataset is linked to a publication, specify the DOI of the publication
[insert DOI reference]	[insert title or identifier]	[YES] [NO]	[YES] [NO]	[insert DOI reference of the publication]

⁵ Accessible means Open Access defined as free of charge access for anyone via Internet. Answer "yes" if the open access to the data is already established or if it will be established after an embargo period.

⁶ Re-usability has 2 aspects: 1) technical: the technical standards used are compatible 2) legal: the necessary rights are in place for other users to use the dataset.

9. Gender

Gender of researchers and other workforce⁷ involved in the project

Beneficiaries	Number Women researchers ⁸ (all levels, incl. postdocs and PhD students)	Number Men researchers ⁸ (all levels, incl. postdocs and PhD students)	Number Women in the workforce other than researchers	Number Men in the workforce other than researchers
[insert name of beneficiary]	[insert number]	[insert number]	[insert number]	[insert number]

(*) Data in coloured fields will be prefilled by the IT tool.

Gender dimension in the project

Does the project include a gender dimension in research content⁹? YES NO

⁷ Figures must be provided in Head Count.

⁸ Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge. They conduct research and improve or develop concepts, theories, models, techniques instrumentation, software or operational methods. (Frascati Manual (2015): §5.35).

⁹ Gender dimension in research content means taking into account as relevant the biological characteristics and the social and cultural features of women and men in the content of the research itself. It does not refer to the gender balance in research team participating to the research project.

[Option only available for projects under "Science with and for Society" (SWAFS)]

10. Science with and for Society

More information on definition of "institutional change" and responsible research and innovation (RRI) approach in the Online Manual.

Institutional changes	Intended target of the project (multiple answers possible)	Beneficiaries
<p><i>[Develop Gender Equality Plans / measures]</i> <i>[Develop material for integration of science and society in curricula (e.g. covering STEM, public engagement, ethics, gender)]</i> <i>[Help uphold human rights and high general ethical standards, by adoption, development and/or implementation of codes of conduct, ethical review, etc.]</i> <i>[Develop activities to anticipate the potential social, environmental, and economic impacts of research (e.g. risk assessment, TA, foresight, Impact assessment, gender analysis)]</i> <i>[Develop a Social Corporate Responsibility dimension to foster responsible innovation]</i> <i>[Help develop R&I standards that enhance social responsibility, inclusiveness, sustainability of R&I processes and products]</i> <i>[Enlarge the scope of R&I activities by fostering informal science education (museums, science centres), promoting citizen science, engaging civil society actors and citizens]</i> <i>[Engage with multiple stakeholders for R&I decision making at local, national, regional EU or global level]</i> <i>[Foster open science and open access to scientific results and data (e.g. on-line open notebooks, open educational resources, open data, etc.)]</i> <i>[Other [insert specification]]</i></p>	<p><i>[The project itself / the project's host]</i> <i>[Universities overall]</i> <i>[Research performing organisation]</i> <i>[Public authorities]</i> <i>[International organisations]</i> <i>[Researchers]</i></p>	<p><i>[insert name of beneficiary]</i></p>

(*) One row per type of institutional change selected from the drop-down menu in the IT tool.]

Project¹⁰ Number: [insert project reference number]

Project Acronym: [insert acronym]

Project title: [insert project title]

Periodic Technical Report

Part B

Period covered by the report: from [insert dd/mm/yyyy] to [insert dd/mm/yyyy]

Periodic report: [1st] [2nd] [3rd] [4rd]

¹⁰ The term 'project' used in this template equates to an 'action' in certain other Horizon 2020 documentation

1. Explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries and Overview of the progress

- Explain the work carried out during the reporting period in line with the Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement.
- Include an overview of the project results towards the objective of the action in line with the structure of the Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement including summary of deliverables and milestones, and a summary of exploitable results and an explanation about how they can/will be exploited⁴.

(No page limit per workpackage but report shall be concise and readable. Any duplication should be avoided).

1.1 Objectives

List the specific objectives for the project as described in section 1.1 of the DoA and described the work carried out during the reporting period towards the achievement of each listed objective. Provide clear and measurable details.

1.2 Explanation of the work carried per WP

1.2.1 Work Package 1

Explain the work carried out in WP1 during the reporting period giving details of the work carried out by each beneficiary/linked third party involved.

1.2.2 Work package 2 Etc.

1.3 Impact

Include in this section whether the information on section 2.1 of the DoA (how your project will contribute to the expected impacts) is still relevant or needs to be updated. Include further details in the latter case.

2. Update of the plan for exploitation and dissemination of result (if applicable)

Include in this section whether the plan for exploitation and dissemination of results as described in the DoA needs to be updated and give details.

3. Update of the data management plan (if applicable)

Include in this section whether the data management plan as described in the DoA needs to be updated and give details.

⁴ Beneficiaries that have received Union funding, and that plan to exploit the results generated with such funding primarily in third countries not associated with Horizon 2020, should indicate how the Union funding will benefit Europe's overall competitiveness (reciprocity principle), as set out in the grant agreement.

4. Follow-up of recommendations and comments from previous review(s) (if applicable)

Include in this section the list of recommendations and comments from previous reviews and give information on how they have been followed up.

5. Deviations from Annex 1 and Annex 2 (if applicable)

Explain the reasons for deviations from the DoA, the consequences and the proposed corrective actions.

5.1 Tasks

Include explanations for tasks not fully implemented, critical objectives not fully achieved and/or not being on schedule. Explain also the impact on other tasks on the available resources and the planning.

5.2 Use of resources (not applicable for MCSA)

Include explanations on deviations of the use of resources between actual and planned use of resources in Annex 1, especially related to person-months per work package.

Include explanations on transfer of costs categories (if applicable).

Include explanations on adjustments to previous financial statements (if applicable).

5.2.1 Unforeseen subcontracting (if applicable) (not applicable for MCSA) Specify in

this section:

- a) the work (the tasks) performed by a subcontractor which may cover only a limited part of the project;
- b) explanation of the circumstances which caused the need for a subcontract, taking into account the specific characteristics of the project;
- c) the confirmation that the subcontractor has been selected ensuring the best value for money or, if appropriate, the lowest price and avoiding any conflict of interests.

5.2.2 Unforeseen use of in kind contribution from third party against payment or free of charges (if applicable) (not applicable for MCSA) Specify in this section:

- d) the identity of the third party;
- e) the resources made available by the third party respectively against payment or free of charges
- f) explanation of the circumstances which caused the need for using these resources for carrying out the work.

ANNEX 2: TEMPLATE OF THE FINANCIAL REPORT

Periodic Financial Report

Individual financial statements (Annex 4 to the GA). More information in the Online Manual. The IT tool will show the applicable financial statement to your type of action.

🖨️ print format A4 landscape

MODEL ANNEX 4 FOR H2020 GENERAL MGA — MULTI

FINANCIAL STATEMENT FOR [BENEFICIARY [name]/ LINKED THIRD PARTY [name]] FOR REPORTING PERIOD [reporting period]

Eligible ¹ costs (per budget category)											Receipts					Additional information				
A. Direct personnel costs			B. Direct costs of subcontracting		[C. Direct costs of fin. support]	D. Other direct costs			E. Indirect costs ²	[F. Costs of ...]		Total costs	Receipts	Reimbursement rate %	Maximum EU contribution ³	Requested EU contribution	Information for indirect costs :			
A.1 Employees (or equivalent)	A.4 SME owners without salary				[C.1 Financial support]	D.1 Travel	[D.4 Costs of large research (infrastructure)]	D.5 Costs of internally invoiced goods and services		[F.1 Costs of ...]	[F.2 Costs of ...]		Receipts of the action, to be reported in the last reporting period, according to Article 5.3.3				Costs of in-kind contributions not used on premises			
A.2 Natural persons under direct contract	A.5 Beneficiaries that are natural persons without salary				[C.2 Prizes]	D.2 Equipment														
A.3 Seconded persons [A.6 Personnel for providing access to research (infrastructure)]						D.3 Other goods and services														
Form of costs ⁴		Actual	Unit	Unit	Actual	Actual	Actual	Actual	Unit	Flat-rate ⁵	Unit	[Unit][Lump sum]								
		a	Total b	No hours	Total c	d	[e]	f	[g]	Total h	I=Q.25 x (a+b+c+f+g) + h x (i) + (j) x (k) - p	No units	Total [l]	Total [m]	n = a+b+c+d+e+f+g+l + i + [j] + [k]	i	m	n	o	p
[short name beneficiary/linked third party]																				

The beneficiary/linked third party hereby confirms that:
 The information provided is complete, reliable and true.
 The costs declared are eligible (see Article 6).
 The costs can be substantiated by adequate records and supporting documentation that will be produced upon request or in the context of checks, reviews, audits and investigations (see Articles 17, 18 and 22).
 For the last reporting period: that all the receipts have been declared (see Article 5.3.3).

📌 Please declare all eligible costs, even if they exceed the amounts indicated in the estimated budget (see Annex 2). Only amounts that were declared in your individual financial statements can be taken into account later on, in order to replace other costs that are found to be ineligible.

¹ See Article 6 for the eligibility conditions

² The indirect costs claimed must be free of any amounts covered by an operating grant (received under any EU or Euratom funding programme; see Article 6.2.E). If you have received an operating grant during this reporting period, you cannot claim indirect costs unless you can demonstrate that the operating grant does not cover any costs of the action.

³ This is the theoretical amount of EU contribution that the system calculates automatically (by multiplying the reimbursement rate by the total costs declared). The amount you request (in the column 'requested EU contribution') may be less.

⁴ See Article 5 for the form of costs

⁵ Flat rate : 25% of eligible direct costs, from which are excluded: direct costs of subcontracting, costs of in-kind contributions not used on premises, direct costs of financial support, and unit costs declared under budget category F if they include indirect costs (see Article 6.2.E)

⁶ Only specific unit costs that do not include indirect costs

Report on Explanations on the use of resources (not applicable for MCSA)

A report on explanations on the use of resources per beneficiary. The report is generated automatically with the information inserted by the beneficiary at the time the financial statements are completed in the IT tool.

Project Number	[project number]
Acronym	[acronym]
Period Number	[1 st] [2 nd] [3 rd] [4 rd]
Period covered	From [dd/mm/yyyy] to [dd/mm/yyyy]

Beneficiary Number	[beneficiary number]
Beneficiary Short Name	[beneficiary short name]

Direct personnel costs

1. Direct personnel costs declared as actual costs (When direct personnel costs are reported in the financial statement, a pop-up window will appear in the IT tool requesting to give information of the amount on person months per WP).

Person months	Associated WP
[insert number pm]	WP1
[insert number pm]	WP2
[insert number pm]	WP3
[insert number pm]	(etc.)

2. Direct personnel costs declared as unit costs (When direct personnel costs are reported as unit costs, including unit costs for SME owners without a salary and beneficiaries that are natural persons without a salary, in the financial statement, a pop-up window will appear in the IT tool requesting to give information on the amount of person months per WP).

Person months	Associated WP
[insert number pm]	WP1
[insert number pm]	WP2
[insert number pm]	WP3
[insert number pm]	(etc.)

3. Use of in kind contribution from third party (When direct personnel costs are reported – as actual or unit costs - in the financial statement, the pop-up window used to give information on the amount of person months per WP will also request details about the use of in kind contribution from third party: the costs, the name and type of the third party and whether the costs were foreseen in Annex 1 or not. Further explanations are mandatory if costs were not foreseen in Annex 1).

Third Party name	Type	Foreseen in Annex 1	Explanations (if not foreseen in Annex 1)	Costs
[insert name]	/Free of charge/ /Against payment/	/YES/ /NO/	[insert comment]	[insert amount in EUR]
One row per third party				
TOTAL				[insert amount in EUR]

Direct costs of subcontracting

(When subcontracting costs are reported in the financial statement, a pop-up window will appear in the IT tool requesting to give information on the costs, description of the subcontract and if the subcontract was foreseen in Annex 1 or not. Further explanations are mandatory if subcontract not foreseen in Annex 1).

Description	Foreseen in Annex 1	Explanations (if not foreseen in Annex 1)	Costs
[insert comment]	/YES/ /NO/	[insert comment]	[insert amount in EUR]
One row per subcontract			
TOTAL			[insert amount in EUR]

Direct costs of providing financial support to third parties

(When direct costs of financial support to third parties (cascade funding) are reported in the financial statement, a pop-up window will appear in the IT tool requesting to give information on the costs and their description).

Description	Costs
[insert comment]	[insert amount in EUR]
One row per item.	
TOTAL	[insert amount in EUR]

Other direct costs: 1. explanation of major actual cost items if the amount exceeds 15% of personnel costs;
2. Unit costs for internal invoicing

1. Other direct costs declared as actual costs: If actual costs declared under "other direct costs" are equal or less than 15% of claimed personnel costs for the beneficiary in each reporting period, no need to give any detail.

If actual costs declared under "other direct costs" are higher than 15% of claimed personnel costs for the beneficiary in each reporting period, major direct costs items need to be recorded in the pop-up window within the IT tool. The record of items must be up to the level that the remaining costs are below 15% of personnel costs, starting from the cost items of highest value in terms of cost amount. If costs were foreseen in the Annex 1 no further explanation is needed. If costs were not foreseen in Annex 1, further explanations are needed.

Short description	Category	Associated WP	Fore seen in Annex 1	Explanation (if not included in Annex 1)	Costs
[insert comment]	[Travel] [Equipment] [Other goods & services]	[insert WP number]	[Y] [E] [S] [N] [O]	[insert comment]	[insert amount in EUR]
One row per item					
TOTAL					[insert amount in EUR]

2. Other direct costs declared as unit costs (When unit costs for internally invoiced goods and services are reported in the financial statement, a pop-up window will appear in the IT tool requesting to give information on the costs and their description)..

Short description	Associated WP	Fores seen in Annex 1	Explanation (if not included in Annex 1)	Costs
[insert comment]	[insert WP number]	[Y] [E] [S] [N] [O]	[insert comment]	[insert amount in EUR]

One row per item				
TOTAL				[insert amount in EUR]

Other direct costs reported as use of in kind contribution from third party

Third Party name	Type	Category	Associated WP	Foreseen in Annex 1	Explanations (if not foreseen in Annex 1)	Costs
[insert name]	[Free of charge / Against payment]	[Travel / Equipment / Other goods & services / Internal invoicing]	[insert WP number]	[YES / NO]	[insert comment]	[insert amount in EUR]
One row per item						
TOTAL						[insert amount in EUR]

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CHANGE
1.0	15.07.2015	Initial version
1.1	14.09.2015	Table on section 12 on Research infrastructures has been corrected.
1.2	08.08.2016	Simplification of the question on energy. Question on gender: distinction between researchers and other work force. Corrections for MSCA.
1.3	27.03.2017	Modification of Part B for Research Infrastructures (RI) actions to include a table with the resources used to provide access to RI.
2.0	19.09.2017	Revision to include the new cost category in MGA v4.0 (other direct costs declared as units costs for internally invoiced goods and services)
2.1	19.12.2017	Update of part B of the template to include explanations on adjustments to financial statements declared on previous periods.

ANNEX 3: COMMENTS FROM THE DELIVERABLE REVIEWERS

Deliverable review form for deliverable quality assessment

Issue	Yes	No	Comments
Is the architecture of the document correct?	X		
Does the architecture of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		But suggestions are made to include templates for interim reports and more info on budget (incl., budget available and eligible costs)
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?		X	Table of content does not match section in the draft reviewed (probably just needs an update)
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?			N/A
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?		X	Not yet in this draft
Are the indexes correct?			N/A
Is the written English correct?	X		
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X		
Glossary present in the document?		X	Not needed

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For comments in the text and suggestions please use track changes and rename the draft version ending the version name with your institution shortname and your name initials.

EJ: GearingRolesProjectHandbook_v.UDEUSTO_MLB

Deliverable review form for deliverable quality assessment

Issue	Yes	No	Comments
Is the architecture of the document correct?	X		
Does the architecture of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?		X	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?			
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?		X	
Are the indexes correct?			
Is the written English correct?	X		
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X		
Glossary present in the document?		X	

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For comments in the text and suggestions please use track changes and rename the draft version ending the version name with your institution shortname and your name initials.

EJ: GearingRolesProjectHandbook_v.UDEUSTO_MLB

ANNEX 4: REFERENCES

European Institute for Gender Equality (2016) Gender equality in academia and research. GEAR tool, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.

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Wenger, E., W. Snyder (2000). Communities of Practice: The organizational frontier. Harvard Business Review, Jan-Feb 2000, pp. 139-145.